

An Enemy of the People A Reflection of Society's Past, Present, and Future

By

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Introduction

An Enemy of the People by Henrik Ibsen has a rich history of controversial productions, with impacts felt across generations and cultures. The issues discussed in *An Enemy of the People* continue to plague us in the 21st century, offering poignant commentary on the role of the press in politics, how environmental concerns intersect with economic realities, and the role of the individual in a democratic society. In the last decade, *An Enemy of the People* has seen a surge in modern productions and adaptations which fill the needs of the communities they serve. For example, a version produced in Flint, Michigan focused on the contaminated drinking water and the vilification of Dr. Stockmann as a harbinger of news society did not want to accept (Shtier). Using the text, research, and design processes I will interpret *An Enemy of the People* through the lens of corporate greed in relation to the pharmaceutical industry and the environmental havoc created by the industry. Through the use of design approaches, research, and supporting materials in the major theatrical design areas I will present my own spin on this timeless classic to reflect the issues of modern day America.

Synopsis and Analysis

An Enemy of the People was written by Henrik Ibsen in 1882. The play follows the struggle of Dr. Stockmann, a doctor in a small Norwegian town famous for its medical baths. When Dr. Stockmann discovers that the baths are contaminated with parasites, he sees this as his chance to be the savior of the town. The editors of the local newspaper “The People’s Messenger”, Hovstad and Billings, agree to print Dr. Stockmann’s findings and are excited at the prospect of being able to shake up the established local governance. Aslaksen, a popular local tradesman, warns Hovstad, Billings, and Dr. Stockmann that they will get better results through

more moderate approaches and cooperation, but ultimately agrees to print Dr. Stockmann's findings. Dr. Stockmann's brother, Peter, the mayor and the Chairman of the bath's medical board, tries to convince the Doctor and the newspaper editors that printing these results could force the baths to shut down, devastating the local economy. The newspaper editors eventually agree with Peter and instead print an article reassuring the town of the baths safety, assuring them that the baths will not be shut down. Dr. Stockmann is incensed and decides to hold a town hall to share his findings directly with the people instead. At this town hall, Dr. Stockmann goes on a tirade about the hypocrisies of free press, a democratic society, and insults the intelligence and integrity of the community. By the end of the meeting everyone in the town hall is enraged against him, calling him "an enemy of the people" and shouting him out of the meeting. The next day, his daughter is fired from her job, and his father-in-law purchases majority shares in the spa in order to try to convince Dr. Stockmann to retract his statements. Peter frames this purchasing of shares as proof that Dr. Stockmann was lying all along and he was only doing this to drive down the stock prices so he could benefit. Hovstad and Aslaksen accept Peter's assertions readily as they cannot believe that Dr. Stockmann truly had the town's best intentions at heart. Dr. Stockmann decries the masses that would portray him in such a light and declares himself an outcast but stays true to his principles and decides to stay in the town and continue the fight.

This play is rich in controversy, and indeed the origins of the play itself reflect this. It is thought that Ibsen wrote this play in response to criticisms of his previous play, *Ghosts*, which discussed an upper middle class family and their struggle with hereditary syphilis. The word syphilis was banned from being printed or spoken in any piece of literature or performance where women could possibly see or hear the word, and theater critics and the general public alike were scandalized by this work (Sprinchorn). Ibsen was incredibly frustrated with the response to

Ghosts, and we can see this reflected in Dr. Stockmann's tirade at the end of the play. In a letter to his Publisher, Ibsen said "Dr. Stockmann and I . . . agree on so many subjects. But the doctor is more muddle-headed than I am, and moreover he has other idiosyncrasies that permit him to say things that would not be taken so well if I myself said them"(Sprinchorn). One of the prevailing themes that Dr. Stockmann, and by extension Ibsen, struggles with is the role of an individual in a democratic society. Towards the end of the ill-fated town hall meeting, Hovstad states that "The majority always has right on its side" to which Dr. Stockmann responds "Who is it that constitute the majority of the population in the country? . . . The majority has might on its side-unfortunately; but right it has not. . . . The minority is always in the right". Ibsen asks us to consider; do the few who stand mightily by their convictions, as is in the case of Dr. Stockmann, therefore have the moral standing to denounce an entire population? This concept can be applied to many social and moral movements throughout history. In a timeless battle, does David have the right to stand against Goliath? Can one individual truly stand against the forces of the masses and make a change in society?

In this case, Dr. Stockmann is also aided by scientific evidence that, tragically, only himself and his daughter Petra seem to hold much stock in. Aslaksen, who supported Dr. Stockmann initially, changed his tune once he heard that it would shut down the baths for two years and the cost of the repairs would come out of the taxes of his constituents. In this case, When Peter is trying to convince Aslaksen not to publish the Doctor's article, he positions this as a decision of the town.

"Peter Stockmann. At a provisional estimate, the alterations that the Medical Officer asserts to be desirable will cost somewhere about twenty thousand pounds.

Aslaksen. That is a lot of money, but—

Peter Stockmann. Of course it will be necessary to raise a municipal loan.

Hovstad (getting up). Surely you never mean that the town must pay—?

Aslaksen. Do you mean that it must come out of the municipal funds?—out of the ill-filled pockets of the small tradesmen?

Peter Stockmann. Well, my dear Mr. Aslaksen, where else is the money to come from?

Aslaksen. The gentlemen who own the Baths ought to provide that.

Peter Stockmann. The proprietors of the Baths are not in a position to incur any further expense.

Aslaksen. Is that absolutely certain, Mr. Mayor?

Peter Stockmann. I have satisfied myself that it is so. If the town wants these very extensive alterations, it will have to pay for them”.

By positioning this as a decision and a burden that the general public must decide to take on, Peter Stockmann is removing any form of culpability for the situation. However, it was revealed early on that Dr. Stockmann warned the board of the dangers of contamination if they went ahead with the building as was originally planned. This tactic of blaming the general public for

BP Ad from 2006, Guardian.

environmental disasters in a misleading way is a tactic we see constantly when it comes to advertisements when dealing with the issue of global warming today. To the left is an ad campaign run by BP in 2006, the campaign was aimed at getting consumers to consider their carbon footprint and how they can reduce it. An admirable goal, however nowhere does it mention that in 2019 BP was the sixth largest carbon emitting company in the world, emitting 34.02 billion tons of carbon where the average individual emits 16 tons a year (Guardian).

Looking through the lens of the intersection of media and environmental issues, *An Enemy of the People* asks us to consider what the role of a free press is in a democratic society. An interchange between Aslaksen, Dr. Stockmann, and Hovstad succinctly sum up this conundrum that faces them.

Hovstad. I am not going to print it. I cannot and will not and dare not print it.

Dr. Stockmann. You dare not? What nonsense!—you are the editor; and an editor controls his paper, I suppose!

Aslaksen. No, it is the subscribers, Doctor.

Peter Stockmann. Fortunately, yes.

Aslaksen. It is public opinion—the enlightened public—householders and people of that kind; they control the newspapers.

As previously mentioned, there is much evidence to suggest that Ibsen was using *An Enemy of the People* as a way to vent his frustrations with the press and their slander surrounding the last play he produced. This frustration clearly shines through in the hypocrisy of “The People’s Messenger”. At the beginning of the play, Hovstad is quick to call for a revolution and to use this discovery as the basis for an overhaul of the town’s governance. However, in the face of even slight economic and public pressure, Hovstad and Billings are quick to condemn Dr. Stockmann and accuse him of grandstanding for his own gain. Today, as was true in Ibsen’s time, it is true that the press is often beholden to the benefactors that sponsor them. How, then, do we navigate unbiased reporting when there are often larger groups and figures dictating what can be reported on and how? How does the reporting of a free and unbiased press sway the vote in the court of

public opinion? Looking again at climate change and the history of climate denial from large corporations, we need only look again at their ad campaigns. The image to the right is of an op-ed in the New York Times published in 1984 by Mobil. The op-ed claims that climate change is a myth and that textbooks are lying to the children of the world by saying that climate change is a threat to their future. Similar to “The People’s Messenger” in *An Enemy of the People*, in the face of overwhelming scientific evidence of global warming and climate change, newspapers across America continued to spread misinformation on climate change for decades to come.

Lies they tell our children

“I don’t have a future.”

With tears streaming down her face, a 13-year-old girl made this bleak assessment to her father. To back up her pessimism, she had brought home from school a mimeographed sheet listing the horrors that awaited her generation in the next 25 years: Worldwide famine, overpopulation, air pollution so bad that everyone would wear a gas mask, befouled rivers and streams that would mandate cleansing tablets in drinking water... a greenhouse effect that would melt the polar ice caps and devastate U.S. coastal cities... a cancer epidemic brought on by damage to the ozone layer.

Moved by the girl’s misery, her father, Herbert I. London of the Hudson Institute and New York University, wrote a book, *Why Are They Lying to Our Children?* The book documents how some of the myths of the 1960s and 1970s—and some much older than that—are being perpetuated and taught as gospel truth in some of our schools. And the book raises a question in our minds: Will the next generation have any better understanding of science and technology—both their merits and their problems—than our own?

Professor London’s book is not a plea for unbridled technology. But it is a plea for balance. And school textbooks, he believes, are notoriously unbalanced. In dealing with environmental questions, for example, no textbook the professor could find made any mention of the following facts.

■ Total automobile emissions of hydrocarbons, carbon monoxide, and nitrogen oxide

in the U.S. are less than half what they were from 1957 to 1967.

■ The amount of unhealthy sulfur dioxide in the air has been steadily declining since 1970.

■ The bacteria level in the Hudson River declined by more than 30 percent between 1966 and 1980.

Textbooks, Professor London finds, mythologize nature as eternally benign until disturbed by man. It’s a rare schoolbook that talks about volcanoes belching radiation into the air, floods that overwhelm river towns, and tornadoes that lift people into oblivion. Moreover, textbooks hardly mention the promise of a bright future already on the horizon—when average life expectancy may approach 90 years, when products derived from recombinant DNA research will eliminate most viral diseases, when we will enjoy greater leisure, and materials—especially plastics—will be better, stronger, and safer.

Professor London’s conclusion—with which we heartily agree—is that we should help our children think for themselves and reach balanced conclusions. Let’s look at their textbooks, not to censor them but to raise questions. Let’s give them different points of view and help discuss them. That way we can educate a new generation of citizens who aren’t scared by science, and who won’t be swayed by old mythologies.

Our youngsters do have a future. We, and the schools, should help them look forward to it with hope, even as they prepare to deal with its problems.

Mobil

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Mobil Op-Ed from the New York Times 1984

Modern Adaptations:

In the last decade there has been a surge of reprisals and adaptations of *An Enemy of the People* in the United States. Some of the most notable adaptations include an adaptation by Tomas Ostermeier in 2018, an adaptation by Arthur Miller in 1950, an adaptation in Flint Michigan in 2017, and an adaptation in Chicago by the Guthrie theater group also in 2017. In 2017 there were eight productions of *An Enemy of the People* across the US, up from two productions in 2016 (NY Times). In looking at the political environment of 2016-2017, it was a very fraught time in

the history of the United States with extreme political ideologies on either side, dealing with issues of free press and

Google Ngram Viewer of the usage of the phrase “An Enemy of the People” from 1800 to 2023.

environmental concerns very reminiscent of ideas discussed in *An Enemy of the People*. It is no

Tweet from Donald Trump on February 17th 2017.

wonder that this Ibsen play from the 1880s was at the forefront of many theaters' seasons. The use of the phrase *An Enemy of the People* itself correlates with the popularity of the play. We see a huge spike in the usage in the 1950s during the height of Mccarthyism, and then again in the late 2010s with the political tensions surrounding Donald Trump, in fact he even tweeted the phrase "It is the enemy of the American People".

In each selected adaptation there is a different emphasis placed on the changes made to the script. In Arthur Miller's adaptation in 1950, Dr. Stockmann is made out to be much more of a simplistic and idealistic hero. In Ibsen's version, Dr. Stockmann, while undeniably in the right, is a selfish, egotistical and arrogant man. While he is not unkind, he is not a likable character. Miller turns him into more of a golden hero, unequivocally in the right and unjustly persecuted by the community around him. In the 1940s-1950s, we see several shining examples of simplified "good vs bad" in all sorts of popular media of the time. The popularity of Marvel comic stars such as Captain America is one such example. Dr. Stockmann becomes the hero who always has the last word, and some of his more extreme ideas and outbursts are removed from the script entirely.

"Miller, on the other hand, does not really challenge the primacy of democracy, nor does he let his hero claim that the majority is always wrong. Instead, he sets forth a few

well-tempered arguments showing that the majority can err, and concludes: ‘The majority is never right until it does right.’ (Miller, pp. 165-166) ”(Bronsen, 240).

Miller adapted *An Enemy of the People* to fit the desires of the audience at the time, true to the theme of escapism in the post-WW2 era seen in the bright shiny lights of the movie musicals of the time such as “Singing in the Rain”, “White Christmas”, and “Guys and Dolls”.

In contrast, Tomas Ostermeier’s adaptation of *An Enemy of the People* did nothing to minimize the more extreme views and passions of Dr. Stockmann. Instead, Ostermeier takes these ideas and directs Dr. Stockmann’s grievances at modern problems. Instead of the water of the spas being contaminated with parasites, they are contaminated with E. Coli. Dr Stockmann’s issues with public schooling in the town are instead directed towards the overprescription of Ritalin to school kids. Perhaps the most striking feature of Ostermeier’s production is the audience engagement and involvement. In Ibsen’s original version, the town hall at the end is a raucous affair but is still constrained to the stage. In Ostermeier’s town hall, the audience are the judge, jury, and executioner of Dr. Stockmann. The play ends with Dr. Stockmann being assaulted with paint, as he is branded “An Enemy of the People” and is ostracized for standing alone with his outrageous beliefs. Ostermeier’s production had a very successful life. It continues to tour the world, and is coming back to the West End in London with Matt Smith starring as Dr. Stockmann in the Spring of 2024. When the tour went to China in 2018, its engagement was cut short by the government after the audience started shouting free speech slogans during the end town hall (Taipei Times). *An*

Poster for “An Enemy of the People” adapted by Tomas Ostermeier starring Matt Smith, premiering Spring 2024.

Enemy of the People was controversial in Ibsen's time, and continues to be controversial in many of its adaptations today.

While Ostermeier's productions involved a range of issues across the board, the adaptation by a group of theater artists in Flint, Michigan focused mainly on the issues of contaminated water. The contaminated pipes supplying water for the medical baths in Ibsen's Norwegian town is eerily similar to the situation in Flint, where lead pipes are contaminating the town's water supply. One of the directors of the production in Flint, Purni Morell, got the idea to stage *An Enemy of the People* after hearing about the situation in the news and noticed how reminiscent it was of Ibsen's plot (Tran).

“A couple of the actors said, ‘Oh, you adapted this quite heavily to fix the situation,’ when in fact, I haven't—it just is like that,” says Morell. “The parallels are sort of astonishing. They're just gifted to you on a plate; you don't have to do very much.”

Despite the astonishing similarities, the group staging the productions did take some creative liberties. Instead of the infamous scripted Act 5 town hall, they create a real life town-hall through talkbacks with the actors and creative team. This is a unique way to offer the chance for community healing through catharsis but also an opportunity for the community to vent about their situation and the frustration surrounding the inaction of the government. Both Ibsen and Morrell acknowledge that the contaminated water is just a metaphor for what Ibsen saw as a moral rot in the society's foundations, and by extension the governing authorities that let this happen (Tran, Bronsen).

Directorial Approach:

The first time I read *An Enemy of the People* I was immediately struck by the relevance of the issues discussed and by the complexity of the characters. How could a play written in 1882 by a Norwegian playwright reflect our society today so well? Dr. Stockmann is a character who is both straightforward and enigmatic. He wants to do good by the town, by his scientific principles, and by his family. But he largely wants to do these things because he wants to be the hero, the one who gets all the praise for saving the town. When this is withheld from him, he becomes angry and places all the blame on the very people he was trying to save moments before. He is both a congenial man and someone so astonishingly arrogant. It's hard to reconcile the Dr. Stockmann at the town hall with the Dr. Stockmann who happily shared food off his table with strangers. Hovstad and Aslaksen are both so strong in their ideals at the start of the play, and so quick to violate them at the slightest hint of pressure. Both are so quick to praise Dr. Stockmann and encourage his self aggrandizing behavior, but when Peter suggests that Dr. Stockmann was only in it for the money and made the whole thing up, they jump on this explanation immediately. The only character to stay true to himself throughout the play is Peter. From the beginning he is upfront about the fact that he wants to keep himself in power and would in fact take delight at putting down his brother to do so.

While many of the productions and issues I have highlighted focus largely on the social, political, and environmental issues discussed in the play, the inner workings of the Stockmann family and the people closest to them are truly at the heart of this piece. At the beginning of the play, it is established that Dr. Stockmann clearly cares for Peter, and Peter only sees his brother as a waste of resources and intellect. Peter is quick to take responsibility for Dr. Stockmann's idea of having the medical baths in the first place, and is quick to remind Dr. Stockmann that he

was given the title of Medical Officer of the baths by Peter himself. Aslaksen reminds us several times throughout the play that he represents the “compact majority” in the town and his change in opinion is what eventually breaks the public’s goodwill towards Dr. Stockmann therefore damning the entire family to ostracization. Dr. Stockmann’s own father-in-law throws away his whole fortune in order to try to get the Doctor to change his tune. While the play may have many important themes, the plot is entirely driven by the interpersonal relationships of the townspeople and the Stockmann family.

I will be setting my version of *An Enemy of the People* in an advertising company to reflect the often insidious nature of advertising when it comes to environmental issues as reflected in my earlier research. Dr. Stockmann will be their chief medical consultant, Peter will be the CEO of the company, Hovstad and Billings will be the heads of the marketing department, Aslaksen will be the head of the Public Relations department, Petra the assistant to the head of the education department, and Katherine will be Dr. Stockmann’s assistant and wife.

Dr. Stockmann has discovered that their main client, Pharma Chemicals, is using materials that have been contaminated. This contamination is causing harm to the consumers, rendering their advertisements for the product false and misleading. Dr. Stockmann wants to bring this report to the Board of Directors and to the general public. Hovstad and Billings fully support it initially, but ultimately in the face of losing their jobs they end up backing Peter. Aslaksen warns of the public backlash but despite his desire to do the right thing, he eventually backs Peter out of fear of the ramifications for the stockholders.

There will be some minor alterations to the script in order to reflect the new setting, but in general this production will hold true to the original. The final town hall will be a stockholders

meeting with some ensemble members sitting around the edge of the tongue of the stage to imply that the audience is also a part of the board meeting. Dr. Stockmann will address the audience directly during his final speech to ask the audience to consider these tough questions right along with the rest of the characters. The largest deviation from the original production in all of the adaptations has been the town hall scene, and my concept is no different. I want the audience to feel like they have a seat at the table and are in a sense complicit in the scene unfolding before them.

Design Approaches:

Scenic/Props

I am setting this in the Young Theater at California State University Fullerton, which is a thrust stage. Because I am setting this production in an advertising company, the set will be an office building. As much of the original play takes place at Dr. Stockmann's house, for my adaptation his house will be replaced with his office, and Katherine's

Image from the Erddig House by Heather Broster.

dinner and hot toddies in the first act will be replaced with bagels and coffee. The back of the set will be office type walls with three sets of doors in the back, with the center doors will be larger double doors. The back walls of the set will be raised a step or two to offer playing space with power dynamics built into it. There will be desks and chairs that can be rearranged, removed, or added during scene changes. The set will be monotone colors, and the floor will be linoleum like is found in most office buildings. There will be fluorescent ceiling lights strung over the thrust part of the stage to add to the office ambience. The first scene will be set in Dr. Stockmann's

office which will have one well loved, large oak desk up center stage. There will be several comfortable love-seats, armchairs, and ottomans spread throughout the thrust part of the stage and a long coffee table running down the middle. The second scene will be in the same setting, but some extra books and papers and empty coffee cups will be added to the scene to make it seem a little more scattered and to show the passage of time. The third scene will take place in the Publicity/Marketing department office. A sign will fly in above the back wall of the set, and Dr. Stockmann's desk will be removed. Three smaller desks will be placed along the thrust stage, one belonging to Aslaksen, Hovstad, and Billings respectively. The center doors upstage will serve as the main entrances and exits in this scene. The fourth scene will take place in Captain Horster's conference room in the same building. The three desks from before will be repositioned to create a long conference table with some ensemble members joining Hovstad, Billings, and Aslaksen at the table and along the edge of the stage to fill out the membership. Two desks and a podium will be placed upstage in front of the back wall so that the speakers can be distinguished. In the fifth scene we will return to Dr. Stockmann's office setting from the beginning of the show, but there will be much disarray, chairs will be overturned, books and papers will be scattered, and there is a general sense of mayhem and defeat.

Lights

The lighting for this show will be mainly in a cool and bright color palette, reminiscent of an office building. The first scene will have some warmer tones, to represent that Dr. Stockmann's office has more of a warmer feeling, a place where he tries to make people feel at home. The fluorescent lighting strips will be dim in this scene, and are mostly providing a sense of mise-en-scene. In the second scene I will keep this warmer tone but transition into a cooler harsh light as Peter and Dr. Stockmann begin to argue. While they are arguing, the fluorescent light

strips will begin to glow brighter. The third scene will be a cool lighting look with the fluorescent

Vonn Lighting Company

lights at a medium intensity as the warm lighting recedes. There will be table lamps at each of the desks to create some of this warmer ambiance to show that Billings, Hovstad, and Aslaksen haven't entirely given way to the harsh realities that Peter is pushing. The fourth scene will be filled with completely harsh and cool lighting, with the

fluorescent lights increasing in intensity as the argument in the town hall gets more and more intense. The fifth scene will be back in Dr. Stockmann's office, but will keep the harsh and cool lighting from the previous scene. The only warm lighting will be provided by the desk lamp, which Dr. Stockmann will turn off at the end of the play as a final symbolic gesture to end the play.

Tiffany "Dragonfly" Table Lamp

Costumes/Hair/Makeup

The costumes will range from business casual to professional depending on their status. Dr. Stockmann's costume in the first and second scene will have the aesthetic of a beloved professor. In the third scene he will have more of a business casual look. For the fourth scene he will have full on professional attire for the town hall. For makeup he will have perpetually rosy cheeks, some frown lines and eye bags that get deeper and darker as the show progresses. Katherine and Petra will both be wearing pencil skirts and blouses with kitten heels.

Dark Academia Aesthetic, X user Edwin Krause

Petra will have different blazers and scarves to show the passage of time in different scenes, as well as an overcoat in Act 3. Katherine will have different sweaters that correspond to the details in Dr. Stockmann's costumes, suggesting that she picks his outfits and matches little details to him. Both women will have simple professional makeup looks. Hovstad and Billings will start the first act in young professional chic with blue and red sweaters, dress shirts, dress pants, dress shoes, overcoats, and hats. In the second scene they will remove the sweaters and hats, but otherwise keep the same look. In the third scene they will wear different sweaters, in keeping with the red and blue color palettes they wore initially. Both will have basic neutral makeup, they are younger and their makeup will reflect that. Aslaksen will wear a suit and tie, but it is an ill-fitting suit. Nice, but second hand perhaps. He will wear the same suit throughout, adding an overcoat and hat in the first and second acts. He is a little older than Billings and Hovstad and thus his makeup should reflect that. Peter Stockmann will be wearing a full-on suit and tie, business professional, definitely the nicest dressed character. He will wear the same suit throughout as it wouldn't be out of the ordinary for businessmen of his nature to have a closet filled with the same outfit. His makeup should be neutral basic with some darker eye bags. Captain Horster will dress similarly to Billings and Hovstad, and can have just one base costume throughout the show. He should be a little bit disheveled and a little lower class than the other two.

Sound

Most of the sound effects will be adding to the ambiance aside from some diegetic sound effects such as phones ringing and perhaps doorbells. The preshow music will be elevator jazz music with a background of office ambient noise. Underscoring the whole show will be the buzz of fluorescent lighting. The buzz will get louder as the fluorescent lights get brighter to show the

tension in particular moments. The transition sounds between each scene will be the mutterings of a large crowd, as if they are closing in on Dr. Stockmann and get progressively louder as we get to the end of the play. Going into each scene, there will be an abrupt cut out of all the noise, and just the hum of the lights should be heard. At the end of the play, there should be a playlist of upbeat and relevant songs such as “Big Yellow Taxi” by Joni Mitchell playing during the curtain call and as the audience is exiting the house. “Big Yellow Taxi” is a song about the dangers of capitalistic greed, and gives the general vibe I will be going for in the post-show music.

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lint/).

Scenic Research
Images:
An Enemy of the People

By: Emily Mattson

General Office Inspiration

Overall Setting Vibes

Cluttered, busy, warm

Symmetrical, busy, clean

I like tiling on the floor with the accent wall and the dark colors on the back wall, as well as the lightwood desks to contrast it.

Again, I like the accent wall with the simplistic desks and open floor plan.

Color palette ideas
for the scenic
elements.

Dr. Stockmann's
Office/Desk

I like the warm feeling from the lamps and the cluttered desk with lots of books and papers.

I like the dark wood desk and bookshelf, I like the globe and the chair as well.

I like the dark wood with the dark blue wall. I also like the red chair.

The mess of papers, books, pens, and other personal items for the top of Dr. Stockmann's desk.

Again, the cluttered nature of the desk with the warm lamps are what I'm going for.

I like the overall warm lighting with the dark woods of the desks and floor.

For the center table, a long dark wood, low coffee table that the characters can gather around at with low backed couches and stools.

For seating in Dr. Stockmann's office, looking at lowbacked furniture as well as stools and ottomans scattered around the thrust part of the stage.

News Office and
Board Meeting
Furniture

Very plain, sleek desks.
Very different than Dr.
Stockmann's solid
wood style. Will be
reconfigured to create
the board meeting
setup.

For both the Newspaper Office Scenes, and the Board Meeting in Act 4, I like the short-backed rolling office chairs. For the Board Meeting, can add more of the same type of chair for the Stockmann family, and extra board meeting personnel along the sides.

Lighting Fixture Inspiration

The overall office vibe with the fluorescent overhead lighting that I am going for.

Individual lighting strips with casing and without casing.

(Top and Left)
Dr. Stockmann's
desk lamp ideas,
should be more
elaborate and
decadent than
the newspaper's
lamps.

(Top and Left)
Ideas for the
newspaper
editor's desk
lamps, a little
more plain but
still of this time
period.

1. Cover Sheet

2. Ground Plan

3. Centerline Section

4. Full Frontal Elevation

5. Full Side View

6. Platforms A and B

7. Platforms C and D

8. Side and Upstage Walls

9. Door Walls

10. Crown Moulding

11. Base Board

12. Door Columns

13. Door Arches

14. Stairs

15. Platform Map

NOTES

(This section is currently blank for notes.)

ENEMY OF THE PEOPLE
 Henrik Ibsen
 DIRECTION Emily Mattson
 SCENERY Emily Mattson
 CLOTHES
 LIGHT
 SOUND
 PROJECTION

CSUF Young Theater

Groundplan
 3/16" = 1'-0"

Assistant LD	Sheet #
Master Electrician	
Date	12/4/22
Revised	

Sheet 2
 of 0

ALL SPECIFICATIONS RELATE SOLELY TO THE APPEARANCE OF THE DESIGN, NOT TO MATTERS OF STRUCTURAL INTEGRITY AND/OR SAFETY. THE DESIGNER IS NOT RESPONSIBLE FOR DAMAGES RESULTING THROUGH THE FAILURE TO EXECUTE THE DESIGNS AND PLANS PREPARED BY THE DESIGNER IN A SAFE AND RESPONSIBLE MANNER. THE DESIGNER IS PERMITTED TO ALTER ANY SPECIFICATIONS WHICH MAY NOT BE COMPATIBLE WITH PROPER SAFETY PRECAUTIONS.

NOTES

ENEMY OF THE PEOPLE

Henrik Ibsen

- DIRECTION Emily Mattson
- SCENERY Emily Mattson
- CLOTHES
- LIGHT
- SOUND
- PROJECTION

CSUF Young Theater

Front Elevation

1/4" = 1'-0"

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1 **Top View Platform A**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

2 **Front View Platform A and B**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

4 **Top View Platform B**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

3 **Right View Platform A and B**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

NOTES

- Build 13 of Platform A
- Build 1 of Platform B
- Cover all Platforms with 2" of Luan

ENEMY OF THE PEOPLE

Henrik Ibsen
DIRECTION Emily Mattson
SCENERY Emily Mattson
CLOTHES
LIGHT
SOUND
PROJECTION

CSUF Young Theater

Platform Details

1" = 1'-0"

Assistant LD	Sheet #
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1 **Top View Platform C**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

2 **Front View Platform C**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

4 **Top View Platform D**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

3 **Right View Platforms C and D**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

5 **Front View Platform D**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

NOTES

- Build 2 of Platform C
- Build 1 of Platform D
- Cover all platforms with 2" Luan

ENEMY OF THE PEOPLE

Henrik Ibsen
 DIRECTION Emily Mattson
 SCENERY Emily Mattson
 CLOTHES
 LIGHT
 SOUND
 PROJECTION

CSUF Young Theater

Platforms C and D Details

1" = 1'-0"

Assistant LD	Sheet #
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of 0

1 **Front View Wall**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

2 **Side View Wall**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

3 **Top View Wall**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

NOTES

- Build 8 for the upstage wall
- Build 4 for the downstage wall on the SR and SL sides

ENEMY OF THE PEOPLE

Henrik Ibsen
 DIRECTION Emily Mattson
 SCENERY Emily Mattson
 CLOTHES
 LIGHT
 SOUND
 PROJECTION

CSUF Young Theater

Upstage Wall

1" = 1'-0"

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1 **Front View Piece A**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

2 **Right View Piece A**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

4 **Front View Piece B**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

5 **Right View Piece B**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

3 **Right View Piece A**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

6 **Top View Piece B**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

NOTES

- Build 2 of Piece A
- Mirror the 2nd Build of Piece A for the other side
- Build 1 of Piece B

ENEMY OF THE PEOPLE

Henrik Ibsen
 DIRECTION Emily Mattson
 SCENERY Emily Mattson
 CLOTHES
 LIGHT
 SOUND
 PROJECTION

CSUF Young Theater

Door Walls

1" = 1'-0"

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CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY
FULLERTON
THEATRE & DANCE

NOTES

- Build 1 of each piece
- Piece A goes on top

ENEMY OF THE PEOPLE
Henrik Ibsen

DIRECTION Emily Mattson
SCENERY Emily Mattson
CLOTHES
LIGHT
SOUND
PROJECTION

CSUF Young Theater

Crown Moulding
1/2" = 1'-0"

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Sheet 10

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1 **Front View Piece A**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

3 **Right View Piece A**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

2 **Top View Piece A**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

4 **Front View Piece B**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

6 **Right View Piece B**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

5 **Top View Piece B**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

NOTES

- Build 2 of each Part
- Part A goes on each side of side doors
- Part B goes between the side doors and the center door

ENEMY OF THE PEOPLE

Henrik Ibsen

DIRECTION Emily Mattson

SCENERY Emily Mattson

CLOTHES

LIGHT

SOUND

PROJECTION

CSUF Young Theater

Base Board

1" = 1'-0"

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1 **Front View Piece A**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

2 **Top View Piece A**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

7 **Front View Piece C**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

9 **Top View Piece C**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

3 **Right View Piece A**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

8 **Right View Piece C**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

10 **Front View Whole Set**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

4 **Front View Piece B**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

5 **Right View Piece B**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

6 **Top View Piece B**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

NOTES

- Build 6 of each piece
- When constructing, align 3 of pieces B and C with the right side of piece A and 3 with the left side of piece A

ENEMY OF THE PEOPLE

Henrik Ibsen

DIRECTION Emily Mattson

SCENERY Emily Mattson

CLOTHES

LIGHT

SOUND

PROJECTION

CSUF Young Theater

Door Details Sides

1" = 1'-0"

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1 **Front View Piece A**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

3 **Right View Piece A**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

7 **Front View Piece C**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

9 **Right View Piece C**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

2 **Top View Piece A**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

8 **Top View Piece C**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

4 **Front View Piece B**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

6 **Right View Piece B**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

5 **Top View Piece B**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

11 **Front View Pieces A, B and C**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

10 **Front View Pieces A and B**
Scale: 1" = 1'-0"

NOTES

- Build 3 of Piece A and 3 of Piece B
- Build 1 of Piece C
- Pieces AB goes over the side doors
- Piece ABC goes over the center door

ENEMY OF THE PEOPLE

Henrik Ibsen

DIRECTION Emily Mattson
SCENERY Emily Mattson
CLOTHES LIGHT
SOUND PROJECTION

CSUF Young Theater

Door Details Tops

1" = 1'-0"

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NOTES

- Build 2 escape stairs

ENEMY OF THE PEOPLE

Henrik Ibsen
DIRECTION Emily Mattson
SCENERY Emily Mattson
CLOTHES
LIGHT
SOUND
PROJECTION

CSUF Young Theater

Stairs

1" = 1'-0"

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NOTES

ENEMY OF THE PEOPLE

Henrik Ibsen

DIRECTION Emily Mattson

SCENERY Emily Mattson

CLOTHES

LIGHT

SOUND

PROJECTION

CSUF Young Theater

Platform Map

1/2" = 1'-0"

Assistant LD	Sheet #
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Props List- An Enemy of the People

Director: Emily Mattson		Prepared by: Emily Mattson		Stage Manager: Emily Mattson		Updated: 2/6/24	
Act	Pg	Item	Quantity	Character	Rehearsal/Show	Consumable	Notes
1		Long Coffee Table	1		R		Preset Furniture
1		Long Low Couch	1		R		Preset Furniture
1		Low Backed Chairs	2		R		Preset Furniture
1		High Backed Chairs	2		R		Preset Furniture
1		Coat Rack	1		R		Preset Furniture
1		Side Tables	2		R		Preset Furniture
1		Side Lamps	2		R		Preset Furniture
1		Bookshelf	2		R		Preset Furniture
1		Papers and Pens	Scattered		R		Preset
1	1	Charcuterie Board	1	Katherine	R	C	Should have meats, cheeses, etc.
1	9	Drink Tray	1	Katherine	R		
1	9	Toddy Glasses	4		R		
1	9	Teapot	1		R		
1	9	Whiskey Bottle	1		R	C	
1	9	Bar Tool Set	1		R		
1	9	Honey	1		S	C	
1	9	Nutmeg/Spices	1		S	C	
1	9	Cigar Box	1		R		
1	9	Cigars	3		S	C	
1	9	Smoking Pipe	1	Dr. Stockmann	S		
1	9	Smoking Cap	1	Dr. Stockmann	S		
1	10	Knitting Project	1	Katherine	R		
1	10	Knitting Bag	1	Katherine	R		
1	10	Textbooks	3	Petra	R		Middle School Textbooks
1	10	Folder with Papers	1	Petra	R		
1	11	Letter	1		R		From the labs
1	15	Scientific Papers	Stack	Dr. Stockmann	R		
2	17	Letter	1		R		From Peter
2	24	Manuscript	1	Dr. Stockmann	R		
2	33	Backpacks	2	Elif and Morten	R		
3	34	Worktables	2	Hovstad and Billing	R		Larger than normal desks
3	34	Press Releases, Marketing Materials	Scattered				For a Pharmaceutical Company
3	34	Desk Materials	As needed				Pens, Papers, Staplers, etc.
3	34	Manuscript			R		Same as in Act 2
3	39	English Book	1		R		Title not shown
3	42	Coat Rack			R		Same as in Act 2
3	42	Hat and Walking Stick	1	Peter			
3	45	Hat and Walking Stick	1	Dr. Stockmann			
3	49	Letter	1	Peter			Official Statement from Peter
4	51	Low Backed Office Chairs	18				
4	51	Podium	1		R		For Board Meetings
4	51	Whistle	2	Citizen 1 and 2			
4	51	Legal Pad and Pen	1	Billing			
4	51	Bell	1	Aslaksen			
5	65	Stones	Handful				As if thrown through the window
5	65	Letter	1				From the Landlord
5	69	Letter	1				Dismissal from the Baths
5	73	Checkbook	1	Morten Kiil			
5	77	Umbrella	1				

5	77	Calling Card	1				
---	----	--------------	---	--	--	--	--

Deck Crew Run Sheet

An Enemy of the People by Henrik Ibsen

Director: Emily Mattson

Prepared by: Emily Mattson

SM: Emily Mattson

Updated: 05/08/24

Crew	Cue	Movement	Item	Dancer/Location	Notes
PreShow Set					
		SWEEP	Stage		
		MOP	Stage		
		CHECK	Spikes		
		SET	Props Tables		
		SET	Papers/Pens	Coffee Table	Scattered
		WASH	Cups, Tumblers, Plates, etc		
		FILL	Tumblers and Bottles		
		PLACE	Charcuterie Items	SR Props Table	
		PLACE	Knitting Basket	Onstage by Armchair	
		PLACE	Coat Rack		
Shift 1	Act 1				
		GIVE	Charcuterie Board	Katherine	
		GIVE	Walking Stick	Peter	
		TAKE	Walking Stick	Peter	
		GIVE	Drink Tray	Katherine	
		GIVE	Cigar Box	Ejlif	
		GIVE	Pipe and Cap	Morten	
		GIVE	Letter	Petra	
		GIVE	Bag of books	Petra	
		TAKE	Stack of Letters	Katherine	
Shift 2	Transition Act 1 to Act 2				
		STRIKE	Charcuterie Board		
		STRIKE	Drink Tray		
		STRIKE	Cigar Box, Pipe and Cap		
		STRIKE	Bag of Books		
		STRIKE	Knitting Project		
Shift 3	Act 2				
		GIVE	Letter	Katherine	
		GIVE	Backpacks	Ejlif and Morten	
Shift 4	Transition Act 2 to Act 3				
		STRIKE	Letter		
		TAKE	Backpacks	Eljif and Morten	
		STRIKE	Scattered pens and papers		
		STRIKE	Armchair		
		SET	Workstations	For Billings and Hovstad	
		PLACE	Scattered marketing materials		
		PLACE	Office Chairs		
Shift 5	Act 3				
		GIVE	Manuscript	Billings	
		GIVE	Walking Stick	Dr. Stockmann	
		GIVE	Letter	Peter	
		GIVE	English Book	Petra	
		GIVE	Walking Stick	Peter	
Shift 6	Transition Act 3 to Act 4				
		STRIKE	Workstations		
		STRIKE	Office Chairs		
		STRIKE	Coat Rack		
		SET	Conference table		
		PLACE	Podium		
		PLACE	Lowbacked office chairs		
Shift 7	Act 4				
		GIVE	Legal Pad and Pen	Billings	
		GIVE	Bell	Asklaksen	
Shift 8	Transition Act 4 to Act 5				
		STRIKE	Podium		
		STRIKE	Office Chairs		
		SET	Coffee Tables		
		PLACE	Armchair		
		PLACE	Coat Rack		
		PLACE	Umbrella	On Coatrack	
		PLACE	Papers	Scattered	
		PLACE	Stones	Scattered	
Shift 9	Act 5				
		GIVE	Letter	Katherine	
		GIVE	Letter	Peter	
		GIVE	Checkbook	Morten	
	Post Show				
		STRIKE	Letters		
		STRIKE	Stones		
		STRIKE	Papers and pens		
		WASH	Charcuterie Board		
		WASH	Glasses and Bottles		

Portrait Gallery:
An Enemy of the People

By: Emily Mattson

Doctor Stockmann

Naveen Andrews

Katherine Stockmann

Laura Dern

Petra
Stockmann

Simone Ashley

Ejlif
Stockmann

Walker Scobell

Morten
Stockmann

Karan Brar

Peter Stockmann

Jude Law

Morten Kiil

Martin Sheen

Hovstad

Simon Bassett

Billing

Henry Golding

Captain Horster

Pedro Pascal

Aslaksen

Idris Elba

Ensemble:
Man

Michael Cimino

Ensemble Woman

Lily James

Costume Research
Images:
An Enemy of the People

By: Emily Mattson

Dr.
Stockmann

Naveen Andrews

Look One (Acts 1, 2, 3)

Light color dress pants, dress shoes, dress shirt, sweater, blazer, tie, long overcoat.

Look Two (Acts 4, 5)

Vest over a dress shirt with a coat and tie, dress pants, dress shoes

Katherine Stockmann

Laura Dern

Look One (Acts 1, 2, 3, 5)

Semi-formal business, dress pants, low boot heels, white blouse, sweater, matching jewelry

Look Two (Act 4)

Dark suit, business professional, low heels, matching jewelry

Petra Stockmann

Simone Ashley

Look One (Acts 1, 2, 3, 5)

Business casual, sweater, nice pants, low boot heel, matching accessories

Look Two (Act 4)

Dark suit, business professional, low heels, matching jewelry, similar to Katherine's

Ejlif
Stockmann

Walker Scobell

Morten
Stockmann

Karan Brar

Look One (Acts 1, 2, 3, 5) Elijf and Morten

School uniform, polo shirt, black pants, black shoes, blazer, tie

Look Two (Act 4)

Dark blazer, dress pants, dress shoes, tie

Peter Stockmann

Jude Law

Look One (Acts 1, 2, 3)

Three piece suit, tie, dress shoes, dress shirt, overcoat

Look One (Acts 4, 5)

Black three piece suit, tie, dress shoes, dress shirt, overcoat

Morten Kiil

Martin Sheen

Look One (Acts 2, 4, 5)

Business casual, blazer, dress shirt, dress pants, dress shoes, good quality

Hovstad

Simon Bassett

Billing

Henry Golding

Look One (Acts 1, 2, 3, 5) Hovstad

Dress shirt, dress pants, dress shoes, sweater over dress shirt, belt

Look Two (Act 4) Hovstad and Billing

Dress shirt, dress pants, dress shoes, sweater over dress shirt, belt, add blazer and tie

Captain Horster

Pedro Pascal

Look One (Acts 1, 4, 5)

Irish sweater, long coat, beanie, slacks, boots

Aslaksen

Idris Elba

Look One (Acts 2, 3, 4, 5)

Dress shirt, dress pants, blazer, dress shoes, belt, not well fitting,
well used

Ensemble:
Man

Michael Cimino

Look One (Act 4 and Transitions)

Business professional, dark suit, dress shirt, tie, dress shoes, belt

Ensemble Woman

Lily James

Look One (Act 4 and Transitions)

Generic business professional, dark suit, dress shirt, dress shoes

Color Swatches

An Enemy of the People

By: Emily Mattson

Dr.
Stockmann

Naveen Andrews

Look One (Acts 1, 2, 3)

Light color dress pants, dress shoes, dress shirt, sweater, blazer, tie, long overcoat.

Look One (Acts 1, 2, 3)

LOOK ONE: White
Shirt, Maroon
Sweater, Tan
Overcoat, Gold
and Grey Tie, Wrist
Watch, Khaki
Pants, Grey Socks,
Black Shoes

Look Two (Acts 4, 5)

Vest over a dress shirt with a coat and tie, dress pants, dress shoes

LOOK TWO: Grey
three piece suit,
pocket watch,
red pocket square,
red tie

Katherine Stockmann

Laura Dern

Look One (Acts 1, 2, 3, 5)

Semi-formal business, dress pants, low boot heels, white blouse, sweater, matching jewelry

LOOK ONE: White
Blouse, Mauve
Sweater, Khaki
Pants, Tan heels,
Pearl necklace,
Pearl Earrings,
Gold Wristwatch

Look Two (Act 4)

Dark suit, business professional, low heels, matching jewelry

LOOK TWO: White Blouse, Black Blazer, Black Pants, Black Heels, Pearl Earrings, Red Purse

Petra
Stockmann

Simone Ashley

Look One (Acts 1, 2, 3, 5)

Business casual, sweater, nice pants, low boot heel, matching accessories

LOOK ONE: Orange Sweater, Grey Blouse, Blue Jeans, Brown Boots, Rainbow Earrings

Look Two (Act 4)

Dark suit, business professional, low heels, matching jewelry, similar to Katherine's

LOOK TWO: White Blouse, Black Blazer, Black Pants, Black Heels, Rainbow Earrings, Brown Satchel

Ejlif
Stockmann

Walker Scobell

Morten
Stockmann

Karan Brar

Look One (Acts 1, 2, 3, 5) Elijf and Morten

School uniform, polo shirt, black pants, black shoes, blazer, tie

LOOK ONE: White Polo, Blue School Blazer, Blue
Pants, Black Shoes, Red Tie, Backpack

Look Two (Act 4)

Dark blazer, dress pants, dress shoes, tie

LOOK TWO: White Dress Shirt, Black Blazer,
Khaki Pants, Black Dress Shoes, Red Tie

Peter Stockmann

Jude Law

Look One (Acts 1, 2, 3)

Three piece suit, tie, dress shoes, dress shirt, overcoat, bowler hat

LOOK ONE: Grey
Three Piece Suit,
Blue Tie, White
Dress Shirt, Blue
Pocket Square,
Brown Dress
Shoes, Brown Hat,
Brown Walking
Stick

Look One (Acts 4, 5)

Black three piece suit, tie, dress shoes, dress shirt, overcoat, bowler hat

LOOK TWO: Black Three Piece Suit, White Dress
Shirt, Black Plaid Tie, Black Dress Shoes, Brown
Briefcase, Gold Pocket Watch

Morten Kiil

Martin Sheen

Look One (Acts 2, 4, 5)

Business casual, blazer, dress shirt, dress pants, dress shoes, good quality

LOOK ONE: Light
Blue Dress Shirt,
Olive Blazer, Tan
Pants, Brown Belt,
Brown Dress
Shoes

Hovstad

Simon Bassett

Billing

Henry Golding

Look One (Acts 1, 2, 3, 5) Hovstad and Billing

Dress shirt, dress pants, dress shoes, sweater over dress shirt, belt

BILLING

LOOK ONE: White
Dress Shirt, Olive
Sweater, Tan
Pants, Brown Belt,
Brown Shoes

HOVSTAD

LOOK ONE: White
Dress Shirt, Blue
Sweater, Grey
Pants, Black Belt,
Black Shoes

Captain Horster

Pedro Pascal

Look One (Acts 1, 4, 5)

Irish sweater, long coat, beanie, slacks, boots

LOOK ONE:
Undershirt, White
Irish Sweater, Long
Grey Overcoat,
Black Slacks, Black
Work Boots, Grey
Beanie

Aslaksen

Idris Elba

Look One (Acts 2, 3, 4, 5)

Dress shirt, dress pants, blazer, dress shoes, belt, not well fitting, well used

LOOK ONE: White
Dress Shirt, Tan
Blazer, Tan Pants,
Brown Dress
Shoes, Brown Belt

Ensemble:
Man

Michael Cimino

Look One (Act 4 and Transitions)

Generic business professional, dark suit, dress shirt, tie, dress shoes, belt

LOOK ONE: White
Dress Shirt, Grey
Suit, Brown Shoes,
Brown Belt, Blue
Tie

Ensemble Woman

Lily James

Look One (Act 4 and Transitions)

Generic business professional, dark suit, dress shirt, dress shoes

LOOK ONE: White
Dress Shirt, Grey
Suit, Low Heels

An Enemy of the People

		Director: Emily Mattson		Costume Designer: Emily Mattson		Presented at CSUF Young Theater		Costume Plot	Updated: 4/18/24	
Actor	Character	Act 1	Transition (:)	Act 2	Transition (:)	Act 3	Transition (:)	Act 4	Transition (:)	Act 5
		Dr. Stockmann's Office		Dr. Stockmann's Office		People's Messenger Office		Town Hall		Dr. Stockmann's Office
Notes										
Naveen Andrews	Dr. Stockmann	LOOK ONE: White Shirt, Maroon Sweater, Tan Overcoat, Gold and Grey Tie, Wrist Watch, Khaki Pants, Grey Socks, Black Shoes	REMOVE: Maroon Sweater	LOOK ONE: White Shirt, Tan Overcoat, Gold and Grey Tie, Wrist Watch, Khaki Pants, Grey Socks, Black Shoes	ADD: Grey Blazer	LOOK ONE: White Shirt, Grey Blazer, Tan Overcoat, Gold and Grey Tie, Wrist Watch, Khaki Pants, Grey Socks, Black Shoes	LOOK ONE to LOOK TWO	LOOK TWO: Grey three piece suit, pocket watch, red pocket square, red tie	REMOVE: Coat	LOOK TWO: Grey three piece suit, pocket watch, red pocket square, red tie
Laura Dern	Katherine Stockmann	LOOK ONE: White Blouse, Mauve Sweater, Khaki Pants, Tan heels, Pearl necklace, Pearl Earrings, Gold Wristwatch	REMOVE: Mauve Sweater ADD: Grey Sweater	LOOK ONE: White Blouse, Grey Sweater, Khaki Pants, Tan heels, Pearl necklace, Pearl Earrings, Gold Wristwatch	REMOVE: Grey Sweater	LOOK ONE: White Blouse, Khaki Pants, Tan heels, Pearl necklace, Pearl Earrings, Gold Wristwatch	LOOK ONE to LOOK TWO	LOOK TWO: White Blouse, Black Blazer, Black Pants, Black Heels, Pearl Earrings, Red Purse	REMOVE: Blazer	LOOK TWO: White Blouse, Black Pants, Black Heels, Pearl Earrings
Simone Ashley	Petra Stockmann	LOOK ONE: Orange Sweater, Grey Blouse, Blue Jeans, Brown Boots, Rainbow Earrings	REMOVE: Orange Sweater	LOOK ONE: Grey Blouse, Blue Jeans, Brown Boots, Rainbow Earrings	ADD: Amber Cardigan	LOOK ONE: Grey Blouse, Amber Cardigan, Blue Jeans, Brown Boots, Rainbow Earrings	LOOK ONE to LOOK TWO	LOOK TWO: White Blouse, Black Blazer, Black Pants, Black Heels, Rainbow Earrings, Satchel	REMOVE: Blazer, Black Heels ADD: Amber Cardigan, Low Boots	LOOK TWO: White Blouse, Amber Cardigan, Black Pants, Low Boots, Rainbow Earrings
Jude Law	Peter Stockmann	LOOK ONE: Grey Three Piece Suit, Blue Tie, White Dress Shirt, Blue Pocket Square, Brown Dress Shoes, Brown Hat, Brown Walking Stick		LOOK ONE: Grey Three Piece Suit, Blue Tie, White Dress Shirt, Blue Pocket Square, Brown Dress Shoes, Brown Hat, Brown Walking Stick	ADD: Briefcase	LOOK ONE: Grey Three Piece Suit, Blue Tie, White Dress Shirt, Blue Pocket Square, Brown Dress Shoes, Brown Hat, Brown Walking Stick, Briefcase	LOOK ONE to LOOK TWO	LOOK TWO: Black Three Piece Suit, White Dress Shirt, Black Plaid Tie, Black Dress Shoes, Briefcase, Pocketwatch	REMOVE: Briefcase	LOOK TWO: Black Three Piece Suit, White Dress Shirt, Black Plaid Tie, Black Dress Shoes, Briefcase, Pocketwatch
Henry Golding	Billings	LOOK ONE: White Dress Shirt, Olive Sweater, Tan Pants, Brown Belt, Brown Shoes		LOOK ONE: White Dress Shirt, Olive Sweater, Tan Pants, Brown Belt, Brown Shoes		LOOK ONE: White Dress Shirt, Olive Sweater, Tan Pants, Brown Belt, Brown Shoes	ADD: Brown Blazer, Blue Tie	LOOK ONE: White Dress Shirt, Olive Sweater, Tan Pants, Brown Belt, Brown Blazer, Blue Tie, Brown Shoes		LOOK ONE: White Dress Shirt, Olive Sweater, Tan Pants, Brown Belt, Brown Blazer, Blue Tie, Brown Shoes
Simon Bassett	Hovstad	LOOK ONE: White Dress Shirt, Blue Sweater, Grey Pants, Black Belt, Black Shoes		LOOK ONE: White Dress Shirt, Blue Sweater, Grey Pants, Black Belt, Black Shoes		LOOK ONE: White Dress Shirt, Blue Sweater, Grey Pants, Black Belt, Black Shoes	ADD: Black Blazer, Blue Plaid Tie	LOOK ONE: White Dress Shirt, Blue Sweater, Grey Pants, Black Belt, Black Shoes, Black Blazer, Blue Plaid Tie		LOOK ONE: White Dress Shirt, Blue Sweater, Grey Pants, Black Belt, Black Shoes, Black Blazer, Blue Plaid Tie
Idris Elba	Aslaksen			LOOK ONE: White Dress Shirt, Tan Blazer, Tan Pants, Brown Dress Shoes, Brown Belt		LOOK ONE: White Dress Shirt, Tan Blazer, Tan Pants, Brown Dress Shoes, Brown Belt	ADD: Maroon Tie	LOOK ONE: White Dress Shirt, Tan Blazer, Tan Pants, Brown Dress Shoes, Brown Belt, Maroon Tie		LOOK ONE: White Dress Shirt, Tan Blazer, Tan Pants, Brown Dress Shoes, Brown Belt, Maroon Tie
Martin Sheen	Morten Kiil			LOOK ONE: Light Blue Dress Shirt, Olive Blazer, Tan Pants, Brown Belt, Brown Dress Shoes				LOOK ONE: Light Blue Dress Shirt, Olive Blazer, Tan Pants, Brown Belt, Brown Dress Shoes		LOOK ONE: Light Blue Dress Shirt, Olive Blazer, Tan Pants, Brown Belt, Brown Dress Shoes
Walker Scobell	Ejlif Stockmann	LOOK ONE: White Polo, Blue School Blazer, Blue Pants, Black Shoes, Red Tie, Backpack	REMOVE: Blazer, Backpack	LOOK ONE: White Polo, Blue Pants, Black Shoes, Red Tie			LOOK ONE to LOOK TWO	LOOK TWO: White Dress Shirt, Black Blazer, Khaki Pants, Black Dress Shoes, Red Tie	REMOVE: Blazer and Tie	LOOK TWO: White Dress Shirt, Khaki Pants, Black Dress Shoes
Karan Brar	Morten Stockmann	LOOK ONE: White Polo, Blue School Blazer, Blue Pants, Black Shoes, Red Tie, Backpack	REMOVE: Blazer, Backpack	LOOK ONE: White Polo, Blue Pants, Black Shoes, Red Tie			LOOK ONE to LOOK TWO	LOOK TWO: White Dress Shirt, Black Blazer, Khaki Pants, Black Dress Shoes, Red Tie	REMOVE: Blazer and Tie	LOOK TWO: White Dress Shirt, Khaki Pants, Black Dress Shoes
Pedro Pascal	Captain Horster	LOOK ONE: Undershirt, White Irish Sweater, Long Grey Overcoat, Black Slacks, Black Workboots, Grey Beanie						LOOK ONE: Undershirt, White Irish Sweater, Long Grey Overcoat, Black Slacks, Black Workboots, Grey Beanie		LOOK ONE: Undershirt, White Irish Sweater, Long Grey Overcoat, Black Slacks, Black Workboots, Grey Beanie
Michael Cimino	Ensemble Man 1		LOOK ONE: White Dress Shirt, Grey Suit, Brown Shoes, Brown Belt, Blue Tie		LOOK ONE: White Dress Shirt, Grey Suit, Brown Shoes, Brown Belt, Blue Tie		LOOK ONE: White Dress Shirt, Grey Suit, Brown Shoes, Brown Belt, Blue Tie	LOOK ONE: White Dress Shirt, Grey Suit, Brown Shoes, Brown Belt, Blue Tie	LOOK ONE: White Dress Shirt, Grey Suit, Brown Shoes, Brown Belt, Blue Tie	
Lily James	Ensemble Woman 1		LOOK ONE: White Dress Shirt, Grey Suit, Low Heels		LOOK ONE: White Dress Shirt, Grey Suit, Low Heels		LOOK ONE: White Dress Shirt, Grey Suit, Low Heels	LOOK ONE: White Dress Shirt, Grey Suit, Low Heels	LOOK ONE: White Dress Shirt, Grey Suit, Low Heels	

Makeup Research
Images:
An Enemy of the People

By: Emily Mattson

Dr.
Stockmann

Naveen Andrews

Neutral basic makeup, some wrinkles along brow and smile lines.

Natural curly hair, some product to keep it out of face.

Katherine Stockmann

Laura Dern

Neutral basic makeup, some wrinkles along brow and smile lines.

Hair pulled back into professional bun.

Petra
Stockmann

Simone Ashley

Neutral basic makeup, a little more of a bold lip and mascara,

Natural hair, parted to one side.

Ejlif
Stockmann

Walker Scobell

Neutral Basic Makeup with natural hair,

Morten
Stockmann

Karan Brar

Neutral Basic Makeup with natural hair,

Peter Stockmann

Jude Law

Neutral Basic Makeup with wrinkles added along
brow and smile lines.

Medium slick backed hair.

Morten Kiil

Martin Sheen

Neutral basic makeup with more wrinkles
along brow, smile lines, and jowls.

Medium slick backed hair.

Billing

Henry Golding

Neutral Basic Makeup

Side part with a little product to keep its shape.

Captain Horster

Pedro Pascal

Neutral Basic Makeup with natural hair.
More wrinkle lines to show more of a
weathered look.

Aslaksen

Idris Elba

Neutral Basic Makeup with natural hair,

Ensemble:
Man

Michael Cimino

Neutral Basic Makeup with natural hair,

Ensemble Woman

Lily James

Neutral Basic Makeup

Hair pulled back into professional bun.

Show: An Enemy of the People
Actor: Naveen Andrews
Character: Dr. Thomas Stockmann

Designer: Emily Mattson
Date: 3/5/24

Apply BN Y-1 Lite Olive to whole face and neck using a sponge. Apply TW-21 Ivory to brows, cheekbones, and top of nasal bridge using a sponge. Apply BN P-127 Caramel Tan to temples, below cheekbones, and on the outside edge of nasal bridge using a sponge. Blend all contour and highlight using a sponge. Apply setting powder to the whole face. Using a thin brush, apply BN P-127 Caramel Tan to create brow wrinkles, crows feet, smile lines, and chin dimple. Using a thin brush, apply TW-21 Ivory just below the wrinkles created, as pictured above. Using a sponge, apply LSC-6 Natural Brown to lips. Apply setting powder to whole face.

Show: An Enemy of the People
Actor: Henry Golding
Character: Billings

Designer: Emily Mattson
Date: 3/5/24

Apply BN CT-11 Cameo Beige to the whole face and neck using a sponge. Apply BN CT-15 Vanilla Almond to the brow, cheekbones, top of the nasal bridge, and to the chin using a sponge. Apply BN P-111 Olive Amber to the temples, below the cheekbones, and along the outside edge of the nasal bridge using a sponge. Blend all contour and highlight with a sponge. Apply BN LCS-5 Natural to the lips. Apply setting powder to the whole face.

Show: An Enemy of the People
Actor: Karan Brar
Character: Morten Stockmann

Designer: Emily Mattson
Date: 3/5/24

Apply BN P-7 Bronzestone to the entire face and neck using a sponge. Apply BN L-2 Lite Beige to the brow, cheekbones, top of the nasal bridge, and chin using a sponge. Apply BN P-11 Teak to the temples, below the cheekbones, and along the outside edge of the nasal bridge using a sponge. Blend all contour and highlight using a sponge. Apply BN LCS-6 Natural Brown to the lips using a sponge. Apply setting powder to the whole face.

Show: An Enemy of the People
Actor: Simon Bassett
Character: Hovstad

Designer: Emily Mattson
Date: 3/5/24

Apply BN MA-2 Brown Sugar to the whole face and neck using a sponge. Apply BN TW-23 Fawn to the brow, cheekbones, along the top of the nasal bridge, and on the chin using a sponge. Apply BN Y-5 Olive Tan to the temples, beneath the cheekbones and along the edge of the nasal bridge using a sponge. Blend all highlight and contour using a sponge. Apply BN LCS-6 Natural Brown to the lips using a sponge. Apply setting powder to the whole face.

Show: An Enemy of the People

Actor: Michael Cimino

Character: Ensemble Man

Designer: Emily Mattson

Date: 3/5/24

Apply BN P-7 Bronzestone to the whole face and neck using a makeup sponge. Apply BN CT-09 Bella 002 to the brows, cheekbones, top of the nasal bridge, and chin using a sponge. Apply BN Y-1 Lite Olive to the temples, under the cheekbones, and along the nasal bridge using a sponge. Blend all contour and highlight using a sponge. Apply BN LCS-5 Natural to the lips using a sponge. Apply setting powder to the whole face.

Show: An Enemy of the People
Actor: Simone Ashley
Character: Petra Stockmann

Designer: Emily Mattson
Date: 3/5/24

Apply BN P-125 creme foundation to the whole face and neck with a sponge. Apply BN TW-21 creme foundation with a sponge to the brow, cheekbones, along the nasal bridge, and a spot on the chin. Apply BN PAS-16 Coco Sorbet along the temples, under the cheekbone, and a thin line along the inside of the nasal bridge. Blend all highlight and contour with a makeup sponge. Apply BN LCS-6 Natural Brown to the lips, and apply setting powder to the whole face. Apply a black mascara of your choice.

Show: An Enemy of the People

Actor: Walker Scobell

Character: Elijf Stockmann

Designer: Emily Mattson

Date: 3/5/24

Apply BN P-41 Fairest to the whole face and neck using a sponge. Apply BN P-2 Lite Pink to the brow, cheekbones, top of nasal bridge, and chin with a sponge. Apply BN CT-11 Cameo Beige to the temples, under the cheekbones, and along the side of the nasal bridge. Blend all countour and highlight with a sponge. Apply BN LCS-5 Natural to the lips using a sponge. Apply setting powder to the whole face.

Show: An Enemy of the People
Actor: Lily James
Character: Ensemble Woman

Designer: Emily Mattson
Date: 3/5/24

Apply BN P-45 Olive Fair to the whole face and neck using a sponge. Apply BN P-41 Fairest to the brows, cheekbones, top of nasal bridge, and chin using a sponge. Apply BN CT-09 Bella 002 to the temples and below the cheekbones using a sponge. Blend all contour and highlight using a sponge. Apply BN LCS-6 Natural Brown to the lips using a sponge. Apply setting powder to the whole face. Apply black mascara of your choice.

Show: An Enemy of the People
Actor: Idris Elba
Character: Aslaksen

Designer: Emily Mattson
Date: 3/5/24

Apply BN MA-5 Coffee Bean to the whole face and neck using a sponge. Apply BN PAS-20 Espresso to the brow, cheekbones, the top of the nasal bridge, and chin using a sponge. Apply BN P-8 Dark Coco along the temples and under the cheekbones using a sponge. Blend all contour and highlight using a sponge. Apply setting powder to the whole face. Apply BN P-8 Dark Coco using a brush to create wrinkle lines on the brow, crows feet, smile lines, and chin dimple as shown above. Apply BN PAS-20 Espresso just underneath all wrinkle lines created with the contour using a thin brush. Apply BN LCS-5 Natural to the lips using a sponge. Cover the whole face with setting powder.

Show: An Enemy of the People
Actor: Pedro Pascal
Character: Captain Horster

Designer: Emily Mattson
Date: 3/5/24

Apply BN P-6 Natural Tan to the whole face and neck using a sponge. Apply BN P-4 Ultra Fair to the brow, cheekbones, top of the nasal bridge, and a line down the chin using a sponge. Apply BN Y-1 Lite Oliveto the temples and below the cheekbones using a sponge. Blend all contour and highlight, and cover whole face with setting powder. Apply BN Y-1 Lite Olive to form wrinkle lines on the brow, smile lines, crows feet, and chin dimples using a thin brush. Apply BN P-4 Ultra Fair along the underside of all wrinkle lines as shown above using a thin brush. Apply BN LCS-5 Natural to the lips using a sponge. Cover the whole face in setting powder.

Show: An Enemy of the People
Actor: Martin Sheen
Character: Morten Kiil

Designer: Emily Mattson
Date: 3/5/24

Apply BN L-2 Lite Beige to the entire face and neck using a sponge. Apply BN P-2 Lite Pink using a sponge to the brows, cheekbones, and top of the nasal bridge. Apply BN P-43 Alabaster to the temples and below the cheekbones using a sponge. Blend all contour and highlight using a sponge, and apply setting powder to the whole face. Apply BN P-43 Alabaster using a thin brush to create the brow wrinkles, crows feet, smile lines, chin dimples, and jowls. Apply BN P-2 Lite Pink using a thin brush below all of the wrinkles just created as shown above. Apply setting powder to the whole face.

Show: An Enemy of the People
Actor: Laura Dern
Character: Katherine Stockmann

Designer: Emily Mattson
Date: 3/5/24

Apply BN TW-20 Rice Paper to whole face and neck using sponge. Apply BN CT-15 Vanilla Almond to brows, cheekbones, top of nasal bridge, and chin using a sponge. Apply BN CT-05 Bella 002 to temples, below cheekbones, and on the outside of the nasal bridge with a sponge. Blend all contour and highlight with a sponge. Apply setting powder to whole face. Apply BN CT-05 with a thin brush to create brow wrinkles, crows feet, smile lines, and chin dimple. Apply BN CT-15 Vanilla Almond using a thin brush just beneath wrinkle lines created as pictured above. Apply LSC -5 Natural to lips using sponge. Apply setting powder to whole face. Apply black mascara of your choice.

Show: An Enemy of the People
Actor: Jude Law
Character: Peter Stockmann

Designer: Emily Mattson
Date: 3/5/24

Apply BN TW-20 Rice Paper to whole face and neck using sponge. Apply BN CT-15 Vanilla Almond to brows, cheekbones, top of nasal bridge, and chin using a sponge. Apply BN L-2 Lite Beige to temples, below cheekbones, and along the outside edge of the nasal bridge using a sponge. Blend all contour and highlight with a sponge. Apply setting powder to whole face. Using a thin brush, apply BN L-2 Lite Beige to create brow wrinkles, crows feet, smile lines, and jowls. Apply BN CT-15 Vanilla Almond using a thin brush just below wrinkles as pictured above. Apply BN LCS-5 Natural to the lips using a sponge. Apply setting powder to whole face.

Lighting Research
Images:
An Enemy of the People

By: Emily Mattson

01
Societal
Context
Images

01

Personal
Images

An Enemy of the People			
Idea List		Emily Mattson	
Channel	Purpose	Color	Note
1	Front DR Thrust	R60	
2	Front DC Thrust	R60	
3	Front DL Thrust	R60	
4	Front CR Thrust	R60	
5	Front CC Thrust	R60	
6	Front CL Thrust	R60	
7	Front UR Thrust	R60	
8	Front UC Thrust	R60	
9	Front UL Thrust	R60	
10	Front Platform Steps R	R60	
11	Front Platform Steps C	R60	
12	Front Platform Steps L	R60	
13	Front Platform R	R60	
14	Front Platform C	R60	
15	Front Platform L	R60	
16	Front Door R	R60	
17	Front Door C	R60	
18	Front Door L	R60	
19	Back DR Thrust	R60	
20	Back DC Thrust	R60	
21	Back DL Thrust	R60	
22	Back CR Thrust	R60	
23	Back CC Thrust	R60	
24	Back CL Thrust	R60	
25	Back UR Thrust	R60	
26	Back UC Thrust	R60	
27	Back UL Thrust	R60	
28	Back Platform Steps R	R60	
29	Back Platform Steps C	R60	
30	Back Platform Steps L	R60	
31	Back Platform R	R60	
32	Back Platform C	R60	
33	Back Platform L	R60	
34	Back Door R	R60	
35	Back Door C	R60	
36	Back Door L	R60	
37	Back Vom R	R60	
38	Back Vom L	R60	
39	< Side DR Thrust	R60	

	40	< Side DC Thrust	R60	
	41	< Side DL Thrust	R60	
	42	< Side CR Thrust	R60	
	43	< Side CC Thrust	R60	
	44	< Side CL Thrust	R60	
	45	< Side UR Thrust	R60	
	46	< Side UC Thrust	R60	
	47	< Side UL Thrust	R60	
	48	< Side Platform Steps R	R60	
	49	< Side Platform Steps C	R60	
	50	< Side Platform Steps L	R60	
	51	< Side Platform R	R60	
	52	< Side Platform C	R60	
	53	< Side Platform L	R60	
	54	> Side DR Thrust	R60	
	55	> Side DC Thrust	R60	
	56	> Side DL Thrust	R60	
	57	> Side CR Thrust	R60	
	58	> Side CC Thrust	R60	
	59	> Side CL Thrust	R60	
	60	> Side UR Thrust	R60	
	61	> Side UC Thrust	R60	
	62	> Side UL Thrust	R60	
	63	> Side Platform Steps R	R60	
	64	> Side Platform Steps C	R60	
	65	> Side Platform Steps L	R60	
	66	> Side Platform R	R60	
	67	> Side Platform C	R60	
	68	> Side Platform L	R60	
	69	Front DR Thrust	R14	
	70	Front DC Thrust	R14	
	71	Front DL Thrust	R14	
	72	Front CR Thrust	R14	
	73	Front CC Thrust	R14	
	74	Front CL Thrust	R14	
	75	Front UR Thrust	R14	
	76	Front UC Thrust	R14	
	77	Front UL Thrust	R14	
	78	Front Platform Steps R	R14	
	79	Front Platform Steps C	R14	
	80	Front Platform Steps L	R14	
	81	Front Platform R	R14	
	82	Front Platform C	R14	

83	Front Platform L	R14	
84	Front Door R	R14	
85	Front Door C	R14	
86	Front Door L	R14	
87	Back DR Thrust	R14	
88	Back DC Thrust	R14	
89	Back DL Thrust	R14	
90	Back CR Thrust	R14	
91	Back CC Thrust	R14	
92	Back CL Thrust	R14	
93	Back UR Thrust	R14	
94	Back UC Thrust	R14	
95	Back UL Thrust	R14	
96	Back Platform Steps R	R14	
97	Back Platform Steps C	R14	
98	Back Platform Steps L	R14	
99	Back Platform R	R14	
100	Back Platform C	R14	
101	Back Platform L	R14	
102	Back Door R	R14	
103	Back Door C	R14	
104	Back Door L	R14	
105	Back Vom R	R14	
106	Back Vom L	R14	
107	< Side DR Thrust	R14	
108	< Side DC Thrust	R14	
109	< Side DL Thrust	R14	
110	< Side CR Thrust	R14	
111	< Side CC Thrust	R14	
112	< Side CL Thrust	R14	
113	< Side UR Thrust	R14	
114	< Side UC Thrust	R14	
115	< Side UL Thrust	R14	
116	< Side Platform Steps R	R14	
117	< Side Platform Steps C	R14	
118	< Side Platform Steps L	R14	
119	< Side Platform R	R14	
120	< Side Platform C	R14	
121	< Side Platform L	R14	
122	> Side DR Thrust	R14	
123	> Side DC Thrust	R14	
124	> Side DL Thrust	R14	
125	> Side CR Thrust	R14	

	126	> Side CC Thrust	R14	
	127	> Side CL Thrust	R14	
	128	> Side UR Thrust	R14	
	129	> Side UC Thrust	R14	
	130	> Side UL Thrust	R14	
	131	> Side Platform Steps R	R14	
	132	> Side Platform Steps C	R14	
	133	> Side Platform Steps L	R14	
	134	> Side Platform R	R14	
	135	> Side Platform C	R14	
	136	> Side Platform L	R14	
	137	Top DR Thrust	R60	
	138	Top DC Thrust	R60	
	139	Top DL Thrust	R60	
	140	Top CR Thrust	R60	
	141	Top CC Thrust	R60	
	142	Top CL Thrust	R60	
	143	Top UR Thrust	R60	
	144	Top UC Thrust	R60	
	145	Top UL Thrust	R60	
	146	Top Platform Steps R	R60	
	147	Top Platform Steps C	R60	
	148	Top Platform Steps L	R60	
	149	Top Platform R	R60	
	150	Top Platform C	R60	
	151	Top Platform L	R60	
	152	Top Door R	R60	
	153	Top Door C	R60	
	154	Top Door L	R60	
	155	Top DR Thrust	R14	
	156	Top DC Thrust	R14	
	157	Top DL Thrust	R14	
	158	Top CR Thrust	R14	
	159	Top CC Thrust	R14	
	160	Top CL Thrust	R14	
	161	Top UR Thrust	R14	
	162	Top UC Thrust	R14	
	163	Top UL Thrust	R14	
	164	Top Platform Steps R	R14	
	165	Top Platform Steps C	R14	
	166	Top Platform Steps L	R14	
	167	Top Platform R	R14	
	168	Top Platform C	R14	

	169	Top Platform L	R14	
	170	Top Door R	R14	
	171	Top Door C	R14	
	172	Top Door L	R14	

SYMBOLS

NOTES

- GENERAL**
1. Tick marks indicate 18" spacing.
 2. Please stiffen all pipes against rotation.
- ELECTRICS**
1. Electric trims are from actual stage floor to center of Electric pipe.
- FLOOR MOUNTS**
1. Exact location of all floor mounts TBD by designer in space.
- FOCUS**
1. Please drop all color and frost prior to focus.
 2. Please have spare R132, R119, R114, L209 and blackwrap available at focus.

An Enemy of the People

Henrik Ibsen

- DIRECTION Emily Mattson
 SCENERY Emily Mattson
 CLOTHES Emily Mattson
 LIGHT Emily Mattson
 SOUND Emily Mattson
 PROJECTION Emily Mattson

Young Theater

Light Plot

1:48

Assistant LD	Sheet #
Master Electrician	M.E./Supervisor
Date	4/18/24
Revised	

ALL SPECIFICATIONS RELATE SOLELY TO THE APPEARANCE OF THE DESIGN, NOT TO THE FUNCTIONALITY OF THE DESIGN. THE DESIGNER IS NOT RESPONSIBLE FOR DAMAGES RESULTING FROM THE FAILURE TO DISCOVER THE DESIGN AND PLANS PREPARED BY THE DESIGNER OR A USER AND HERETOFORE, THE DESIGNER IS NOT RESPONSIBLE TO ALTER ANY SPECIFICATIONS WHICH MAY NOT BE COMPATIBLE WITH PROPER SAFETY PROCEDURES.

SYMBOLS

NOTES

- GENERAL**
1. Tick marks indicate 18" spacing.
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An Enemy of the People

Henrik Ibsen
 DIRECTION Emily Mattson
 SCENERY Emily Mattson
 CLOTHES Emily Mattson
 LIGHT Emily Mattson
 SOUND Emily Mattson
 PROJECTION Emily Mattson

Young Theater

Worksheet - < Side

1:48

Assistant LD	Sheet #
Master Electrician	M.E./Supervisor
Date	4/12/24
Revised	

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ALL SPECIFICATIONS RELATE SOLELY TO THE APPEARANCE OF THE DESIGN, NOT TO THE STRUCTURAL INTEGRITY AND/OR SAFETY. THE DESIGNER IS NOT RESPONSIBLE FOR DAMAGES RESULTING THROUGH THE FAILURE TO DISCRETE THE DESIGN AND PLANS PREPARED BY THE OCCUPANT OR A USER AND/OR UNAUTHORIZED PERSONNEL. THE OCCUPANT IS ADVISED TO PREPARED TO ALTER ANY SPECIFICATIONS WHICH MAY NOT BE COMPATIBLE WITH PROPER SAFETY PROCEDURES.

SYMBOLS

NOTES

- GENERAL**
1. Tick marks indicate 18" spacing.
 2. Please stiffen all pipes against rotation.
- ELECTRICS**
1. Electric trims are from actual stage floor to center of Electric pipe.
- FLOOR MOUNTS**
1. Exact location of all floor mounts TBD by designer in space.
- FOCUS**
1. Please drop all color and frost prior to focus.
 2. Please have spare R132, R119, R114, L209 and blackwrap available at focus.

An Enemy of the People

Henrik Ibsen

DIRECTION Emily Mattson
 SCENERY Emily Mattson
 CLOTHES Emily Mattson
 LIGHT Emily Mattson
 SOUND Emily Mattson
 PROJECTION Emily Mattson

Young Theater

Worksheet - < Side

1:64

Assistant LD	Sheet #
Master Electrician	M.E./Supervisor
Date	4/12/24
Revised	2

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 ALL SPECIFICATIONS RELATE SOLELY TO THE APPEARANCE OF THE DESIGN, NOT TO THE FUNCTIONALITY OF THE DESIGN. THE DESIGNER IS NOT RESPONSIBLE FOR DAMAGES RESULTING THROUGH THE FAILURE TO DISCOVER THE DESIGN AND PLANS PREPARED BY THE DESIGNER IN A CARE AND WORKMANSHIP MANNER, THE DESIGNER IS PREPARED TO ALTER ANY SPECIFICATIONS WHICH MAY NOT BE COMPATIBLE WITH PROPER SAFETY PROCEDURES.

SYMBOLS

NOTES

- GENERAL**
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1. Electric trims are from actual stage floor to center of Electric pipe.
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An Enemy of the People

Henrik Ibsen

DIRECTION Emily Mattson
 SCENERY Emily Mattson
 CLOTHES Emily Mattson
 LIGHT Emily Mattson
 SOUND Emily Mattson
 PROJECTION Emily Mattson

Young Theater

Worksheet - < Side

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Assistant LD	Sheet #
Master Electrician	M.E./Supervisor
Date	4/12/24
Revised	

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ALL SPECIFICATIONS RELATE SOLELY TO THE APPEARANCE OF THE DESIGN, NOT TO THE STRUCTURAL INTEGRITY AND SAFETY. THE DESIGNER IS NOT RESPONSIBLE FOR DAMAGES RESULTING THROUGH THE FAILURE TO DISCOVER THE DESIGN AND PLANS PROVIDED BY THE OCCUPANT OR A USER AND UNEXPECTED DAMAGE. THE OCCUPANT IS ADVISED TO PREPARE TO ALTER ANY SPECIFICATIONS WHICH MAY NOT BE COMPATIBLE WITH PROPER SAFETY PROCEDURES.

SYMBOLS

NOTES

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An Enemy of the People

Henrik Ibsen

- DIRECTION Emily Mattson
 SCENERY Emily Mattson
 CLOTHES Emily Mattson
 LIGHT Emily Mattson
 SOUND Emily Mattson
 PROJECTION Emily Mattson

Young Theater

Worksheet - < Side

1:64

Assistant LD	Sheet #
Master Electrician	M.E./Supervisor
Date	4/12/24
Revised	

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ALL SPECIFICATIONS RELATE SOLELY TO THE APPEARANCE OF THE DESIGN, NOT TO THE STRUCTURAL INTEGRITY AND/OR SAFETY. THE DESIGNER IS NOT RESPONSIBLE FOR DAMAGES RESULTING THROUGH THE FAILURE TO DISCRETE THE DESIGN AND PLANS PROVIDED BY THE OCCUPANT IN A SAFE AND APPROPRIATE MANNER. THE OCCUPANT IS ADVISED TO ALTER ANY SPECIFICATIONS WHICH MAY NOT BE COMPATIBLE WITH PROPER SAFETY PROCEDURES.

An Enemy of the People				
Director: Emily Mattson		Updated 4/22/24		
CUE	PG	WHEN CALLED	DESCRIPTION	NOTES
PRESHOW				
1		HOUSE OPENS	Preshow Music	
5		HOUSE HALF	Preshow Announcement	
ACT 1				
10	3	AFTER PRESHOW	Blackout	
15	3	Once Billings is sitting	Lights Up DS	
20	3	Billing: Very likely .	Peter Entrance	
25	6	Mrs. Stockmann: There he is at last, I think .	Dr. Stockmann Entrance	
30	9	Peter: You must excuse me now if I-	Peter Exit	
35	9	Dr. Stockmann: It is an extraordinary thing that the postman doesn't come .	Shift conversation DS	
40	13	Petra: No, not yet, but you shall have it in good time .	Dr. Stockmann Entrance	
45	16	All cheer and the boys peek in	Blackout	
ACT 2				
50	17	Dr. Stockmann in place	Lights Up	
55	17	Dr. Stockmann: If only I can get the things set right. I-	Morten Entrance	
60	21	Dr. Stockmann: Come in!	Aslaksen Entrance	
65	25	Dr. Stockmann: Come in!	Peter Entrance	
70	26	Peter: -and then you would have ruined your native town.	Tone Shift	
75	30	Dr. Stockmann: Peter-if you were not my brother-	Petra Entrance	
80	31	Peter: Goodbye .	Peter Exit	
85	33	Petra: He will not give in .	Blackout	
ACT 3				
90	34	When Billing and Hovstad is Set	Lights Up	
95	35	Hovstad: Come in!	Dr. Stockmann Entrance	
100	39	Hovstad: Come in!	Petra Entrance	
105	41	Petra: I know what to believe. Goodbye .	Petra Exit, Peter Entrance	
110	45	Hovstad: Pretend to be doing something, Aslaksen .	Dr. Stockmann Entrance	
115	47	I see the whole of this broad-minded middle class marching like a victorious army-!	Dr. Stockmann sees Peter's stuff.	
120	48	Peter: What does this tomfoolery mean?	Peter Entrance	
125	50	Peter: Now he has sent her out of her senses, too .	Blackout	
ACT 4				
130	51	When scene has been set	Lights Up	
135	52	Second Workman: It's Billing, who writes for Aslaksen's paper .	Horster and Family Entrance	
140	52	Hovstad: Look -here comes the Mayor!	Peter Entrance	
145	52	Dr. Stockmann Entrance	Dr. Stockmann Entrance	
150	55	Dr. Stockmann: Am I allowed to speak?	Dr. Stockmann Tirade	
155	62	Dr. Stockmann: What does the destruction of a community matter...	Dr. Stockmann Tirade Peak	
160	63	Aslaksen: Both as a citizen and as an individual...	Voting Starts	
165	64	Aslaksen: By the votes of everyone here except a tipsy man, this meeting of citizens declares Dr. Thomas Stockmann to be an enemy of the people.	Voting Announcement	

170	64	Billing: Well, I'm damned if I go and drink toddy with the Stockmanns tonight!	Blackout	
ACT 5				
175	65	When scene is set	Lights Up	
180	69	Dr. Stockmann: Come in!	Peter Entrance	
185	72	Peter: -we have a weapon against you now.	Peter exit, Morten Entrance	
190	76	Dr. Stockmann: Then you go and look for yours in the gutter;	Tone change	
195	77	Dr. Stockmann: Upon my soul, they have escaped after all.	Tone change	
200	80	Petra: Father!	Blackout	
Post Show				
205	80	Stage is Cleared	Bows	
210	85	After Bows	House lights	

An Enemy of the People				
Director: Emily Mattson		Updated 5/16/24		
CUE	PG	WHEN CALLED	DESCRIPTION	NOTES
PRESHOW				
1		HOUSE OPENS	Preshow Music	
5		HOUSE HALF	Preshow Announcement	
ACT 1				
10		AFTER PRESHOW	Transition Music	
15		With Lights Up	Add Evening Background Office	
20	6	Peter: Unfortunately , I must go in a moment-	Whistling Kettle	
25		With Blackout	Transition Music, Fade Evening Background Office	
ACT 2				
30		With Lights Up	Fade Transition Music, Add Morning Background Office	
35		With Blackout	Transition Music, Fade Morning Background Office	
ACT 3				
40		With Lights Up	Fade Transition Music, Add Background Printer Hub Noises	
45		With Blackout	Transition Music, Fade Background Printer Hub Noises	
ACT 4				
50		With Lights Up	Fade Transition Music, Add Crowd Hub Noises	
55		With Blackout	Transition Music, Fade Crowd Hub Noises	
ACT 5				
60		With Lights Up	Fade Transition Music, Add Morning Office Background	
65		With Bows Light Cue	Bows Music, Fade Office Background	
70		After Bows	Postshow Music	